

STANDARDIZED SECURITY DESIGN AND INFORMATION SYSTEM IN NIGERIA EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION.

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Abstract

This paper investigates standardized security design and information system in Nigeria educational institution. The paper disaggregated standardised security design to inter office communication, firewall, virus protection programmes and encryption as explanatory variables while information system remains the dependent variable. Data were generated via Primary source through the use of a structured questionnaire and analysed through multiple regression analysis (ordinary least square). The study found that to inter office communication, firewall and encryption has significant effect on information system while virus protection programmes was found to be statistically insignificant. In essence, it was observed that there is need for every organization to have an information security management system that can adequately provide reasonable assurance and support for IT application and business processes.

Keywords: *Standardized Security Design, Information system, Education Institution.*

1.1 Introduction

Nigeria's founding fathers fought valiantly and successfully to liberate the country from British rule on October 1, 1960. There were expectations that the country would be much stronger under self-rule and would adopt policies to ensure the growth and personal development of people in all fields, which would translate to national development. However, when the topic of Nigeria's educational system is brought up today, the first thoughts that come to mind are a decrease in standards, a degradation in the information system, deterioration of services, and examination malpractices.

Before anything else, there should be a focus on mass marketing syndrome and the like. Education is one of the most visible and visible sectors in Nigeria, commanding

attention and consuming much of the country's scarce resources, and like a home sickness, many Nigerians yearn for, strive for, and try to gain access to more and more of it. Nigerian government at all levels must be active for the sake of national growth. Globally, technology is having an effect.

The internet has had a huge impact on the world's educational institutions. A knowledge infrastructure in terms of protocols and processes is one of the alternatives (Author's Observations. 2020). The Internet is a computing philosophy that seeks to link our daily life objects (computing devices or things) by using the Internet as a networking medium. It also aims to provide information processing capability that will enable things to sense, incorporate, and present data when responding

to all facets of the physical environment (Atzori, Iera, & Morabito, 2010).

The Internet infrastructure is built on a layered architecture style, and it uses this perspective to abstract and simplify object integration, as well as to offer smart services solutions to applications (Jing, Vasilakos, Wan, Lu, & Qiu, 2014). There is something that no educational system can do without. Both parties should have access to school-related information through the internet, but information must be held secret using a reasonable standard security architecture.

Standard security architecture is a high-level system layers, application layer that are composed of internet applications and middleware system, which is an organization that simplifies the creation of applications through interoperability necessity of heterogeneous devices and external and internal hacking. Information System provides prompt and accurate output of data & information for policy decision. Hua and Herstein (2003)

Nigeria's educational institutions have created a modern education management information system infrastructure built on web-based networks that is ready for adoption in a growing number of states in order to increase information quality for stakeholders. An

education management information system is a system used to capture, integrate, process, retain, and disseminate an interconnected collection of appropriate, accurate, unambiguous, and timely data and information to education executives, policy makers, planners, and managers at all levels in order for them to fulfil their roles in order to meet an organization's goals and objectives (Wako, 2003).

Both workers of the organisations, whether academics or non-academics, have information. The majority of this information is available in a variety of formats, and these types of information have different values within an entity. With a wide variety of information institutions facing internet security challenges, it is critical to enforce uniform security systems (design), which Brykczynski and Small (2003) believe the security design methodology will assist in implementing. Maintaining and improving the interconnected collection of rules, controls, and procedures that guarantee the integrity of an organization's information properties must be done in a way that is suitable for the organization's strategic goals.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Because of the ever-increasing number of users connected to the internet, the internet is becoming extremely congested; security has become increasingly critical. " The number of computers connecting to the internet continues to grow exponentially, from about 497 million

in 2015 to more than 637 million in 2018. (Parenty, 2019).

Nigeria's educational establishments are not immune to this. As many advantages as online platforms have, new advancements can pose new risks to information technology systems. Organizational security frameworks currently include: inter-office communication systems, firewalls, malware detection services, encryption, and so on, while future systems will need new Extensible Mark-up Language (XML) standard formats such as XML Encryption, XML Digital Signature, and XML Key Management Systems to structure security data.

While XML solves several issues, it has also raised security concerns that must be addressed. The primary goal of traditional security framework design is to enforce effective measures to remove or mitigate the effect that multiple security-related risks and weaknesses can have on an enterprise. Through doing so, Information Security Management would allow the company to enforce attractive qualitative characteristics of its services (such as service compatibility, data protection and integrity).

According to Pattinson (2007), "an information management system architecture focuses on designing information security within an organisation, a topic that is of growing interest to many organisations as they contend with the problems faced by the information society." These issues include emerging information protection and privacy

laws, written rules, cyber security, and environmental (fire, storm, earthquake, tornado) or human risks (Viruses, spam, privacy, hacking, and industrial espionage).

The National Institute of Standards and Technology has proposed sets of more detailed principles for protecting information technology infrastructure (NIST). The Principles were derived from the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development's (OECD) Guidelines for the Security of Information Systems. These standards serve as a foundation for organisations to develop and assess their IT security systems. A substantial amount of effort has also been used in the assessment of defense options.

Much exposure has not been paid to this in Nigerian educational institutions for proper considerations. Universities, polytechnics, and colleges in Nigeria should be aware of this. Nigeria's educational system must look beyond analogue and accept digital with an appropriate information security system. On this basis, the paper aimed to assess the uniform defense design and information structure of Nigeria's educational system.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The core focus of this paper is to investigate on standardized security design and information system in Nigeria educational institution. Specifically, the paper set to achieve the underlisted specific objectives;

1. ascertain the effect of inter-office communication on information system in Nigeria education institution.

2. evaluate the effect of firewalls on information system in Nigeria education institution.
3. determine the effect of virus protection programmes on information system in Nigeria education institution.
4. investigate the effect of encryption on information system in Nigeria education institution.

1.4 Research Questions

The research paper is guided by the underlisted research questions;

1. what effect has inter-office communication on information system in Nigeria education institution?
2. To what extent has firewalls affected information system in Nigeria education institution?
3. What is the effect of virus protection on information system in Nigeria education institution?
4. What effect has encryption on information system in Nigeria education institution?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following research questions were subjected to empirical testing;

1. **H₀**: there is no significant relationship between inter-office communication and information system in Nigeria education institution.

2. **H₀**: there is no significant relationship firewalls and information system in Nigeria education institution.
3. **H₀**: there is no significant relationship virus protection and information system in Nigeria education institution.
4. **H₀**: there is no significant relationship encryption and information system in Nigeria education institution.

1.6 Scope of the study

The content scope of this paper is to investigate on standardized security design and information system in Nigeria educational institution. Standardized security design was disaggregated into inter-office communication, firewalls, virus protection and encryption as explanatory variables while information system as proxy for dependent variable.

2.1 Literature review

2.1.1 Information system

Information consists of data being processed and made meaningful to the users while system consists of set of components used to operate together to make possible conversion of data into information for use by any decision maker within or outside an organization (Davis & Olson, 1985; McLeod, 1995). Information system is also known as computer based information system. In general, the term information system refers to a system of people, data records and activities that process the data and information in an organization

which includes the organization manual and automated process.

Educational institution should have in information system security officers. These set of individuals perform the following roles to ensure the safety of information within the organization via internet or off-lines. Information system security officers must request persons responsible for information systems to establish a method to maintain security throughout the information system's lifecycle. Information system security officers must define security requirements for information systems. Requirements for systems which provide online application and notification services between employees, organizations, and the government must be formulated based on the "Guidelines on Risk Assessment and DigitalSignature/Authentication Fore-Governments'. Integrated Payment and Personal InformationSystem (IPPIS). Information system security officers must define measures for hardware procurement (including leasing), software development, information security function configuration, information security threats, and information system components in order to meet the security requirements of information systems. Information system security officers must examine the necessity of monitoring the information system for information security violation or threats, and formulate the necessary measures if it is deemed necessary.

There are various types of information systems, for example: transaction processing

systems, office system, decision support system, knowledge management systems, data management systems, and office information systems. Critical to most management are management technologies, which are typically designed to enable humans to perform tasks for which the human brain is not well suited, such as: handling large amounts of information, performing complex calculations, and controlling many simultaneous processes (Kock et al., 2002).

Today's information systems are complex collections of technology (i.e., hardware, software, and firmware), processes, and people, working together to provide organizations With the capability to process, store, and transmit information in a timely manner to support various missions and business functions. Information needs to be available, accurate and up-to-date to enable an organization make good business decisions. While various information security system frameworks have been implemented and adopted by organizations, the focus has been more on the use of technology as a means of securing information systems. However, information security needs to become an organisation-wide and strategic issue, taking it out of the information technology (IT) domain and aligning it with the corporate governance approach.

2.1.2 Conceptualization of standardized security design

In general, security is "the quality or state of being secure to be free from danger. Information security design can be defined as a collection of policies concerned with Information Technology (IT) related risks or Information Security Management (ISM). Information Security design is a documented system that provides security for information and data in an organization. Every organization is faced with the task of providing a comprehensive plan for information security. Caralli & Wilson (2004) opined that modern organizations have a huge challenge on their hands as they must secure the organization in the face of increasing complexity, uncertainty, and interconnection brought about by an unprecedented reliance on technology vis-à-vis legislative policies on security". Carlson (2008) characterizes information security design as "coordinated activities to direct and control the preservation of confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information". He notes the concept of information security design thus: "information security designs an example of applying the management system conceptual model to the discipline of Information Security"

The framework within which an organization strives to meet its needs for information security is codified as security policy. A security policy is a concise statement, by those responsible for a system (e.g., senior management), of information values, protection responsibilities, and organizational commitment. One can implement that policy by taking specific

actions guided by management control principles and utilizing specific security standards, procedures, and mechanisms. Conversely, the selection of standards, procedures, and mechanisms should be guided by policy to be most effective.

To be useful, a security policy must not only state the security need (e.g., for confidentiality—that data shall be disclosed only to authorized individuals), but also address the range of circumstances under which that need must be met and the associated operating standards. Without this second part, a security policy is so general as to be useless (although the second part may be realized through procedures and standards set to implement the policy). In any particular circumstance, some threats are more probable than others, and a prudent policy setter must assess the threats, assign a level of concern to each, and state a policy in terms of which threats are to be resisted. For example, until recently most policies for security did not require that security needs be met in the face of a virus attack, because that form of attack was uncommon and not widely understood. As viruses have escalated from a hypothetical to a commonplace threat, it has become necessary to rethink such policies in regard to methods of distribution and acquisition of software. Implicit in this process is management's choice of a level of residual risk that it will live with, a level that varies among organizations.

The various steps involved in building an information system are:

Step 1: Risk Assessment: An organization-accepted security risk assessment should be done. The goal is to identify assets, threats, vulnerabilities and controls to mitigate risks. Some risks will be accepted and management approval should be attained on this.

Step 2: Top-down approach: Security is a management issue and not just an information technology issue. Hence it is critical that top management plays an important role in building an information security management system like educational information management system (EIMS). Education Management Information System is playing an important role in planning, decision making and monitoring of the schools but there are considerable limitations and challenges across EMIS cells in terms of the use of IT technologies in education management and decision making. Management should encourage a culture within the enterprise to follow security principles.

Step 3: Functional roles: Once the management's approval is attained, functional roles will have to be identified. Depending on the type and size of the enterprise, the roles can vary in type and number. A chief information security officer should be identified who solely owns the information security management system. Other functional roles could include Data stewards, Security awareness trainers etc.

Step 4: Write the policy: The security policy is a document that states the

organization's information security strategy at a high level. The language in the policy is derived from the risk assessment. In order to make the policy acceptable to all stakeholders, the manner in which the policy is expressed should be at a high level and align nicely with the organization's business priorities and goals.

Step 5: Write the standards: Standards are definite requirements that an organization should put forth for everybody to follow. The standards should support the security policy and be measurable. It is good practice to document what the penalties are when standards are not met.

Step 6: Write the guidelines and procedures: Guidelines are recommended ideas for an organization. It should be noted that the effectiveness of an organization's security management will not be measured by the guidelines present. Procedures are step by step description on how to meet the standards or guidelines so that the policy is supported. Procedures are usually targeted at the system level people who actually implement the control.

2.1.3 Frameworks for standardized security design

There are many standardized security design for information security management suitable for educational institution in Nigeria. There are:

Inter-office communications system: Inter-office Communications system electronically link all educational stakeholders irrespective of the level and office for sharing of files, reports,

important email messages, across the internet for fast operations of the organization. And an officer should be appointed to handle the affairs and security matters.

Secondly, the BS7799 standard that was released in 1999 by Li. et al. (2003). They presented this standard as a suitable model for information security. The BS7799 is based on a standard archived by best practices in the information security management area. Organizations have been using their own developed framework earlier. They have concluded that BS7799 together with organization-specific requirement is the most effective way of providing information security.

Firewalls: A firewall is a network security device that monitors incoming and outgoing network traffic and decides whether to allow or block specific traffic based on a defined set of security rules. Firewalls have been a first line of defense in network security for over 25 years. A firewall can be hardware, software, or both. A firewall basically allows a company to set up its own set of online rules for its users. Also, it allows a company to prevent its employees from visiting websites that are not trustworthy and can cause serious damage. Therefore, in this internet-driven era, if you don't have a firewall installed, then the chances are really high that your business might fall into the playground of hackers. Eg Bitdefender Box (Bitdefender Box is a firewall hardware that protects all kinds of smart devices. Once set up, the device blocks malware, prevents passwords from getting stolen, prevents

identity theft and hacker attacks for all internet-connected devices); CUJO AI Smart Internet Security (CUJO AI is a company that utilizes machine learning, data science and AI to provide

network operators with a multi-solution AI-driven software platform); The FortiGate Next Generation firewall by Fortinet is a high-performance network security device that prevents intruders from entering your network; Protectli is another firewall provider that has some of the best firewall devices in the industry.

Virus protection programs: these are internet virus that protect the information system from external access.

Encryption: Encryption is the process of encoding a message or information in such a way that only authorized parties can access it and those who are not authorized cannot. Encryption does not itself prevent interference but denies the intelligible content to a would-be interceptor. Encryption is a way of scrambling data so that only authorized parties can understand the information. In technical terms, it is the process of converting plaintext to ciphertext. In simpler terms, encryption takes readable data and alters it so that it appears random. Encryption requires the use of an encryption

key: a set of mathematical values that both the sender and the recipient of an

encrypted message know. The two main kinds of encryption are symmetric encryption and asymmetric encryption. Asymmetric encryption is also known as public

key encryption. In symmetric encryption, there is only one key, and all communicating parties use the same key for encryption and decryption. In asymmetric, or public key, encryption.

Extensible mark-up language (XML): Extensible Mark-up Language is a mark-up language that defines a set of rules for encoding documents in a format that is both human-readable and machine-readable. Eg XML encryption, XML digital signature and XML key management system.

2.1.4 Security Design Objectives

Protect the company and its assets,

Manage Risks by identifying assets, discovering threats and estimating the risk,

Provide direction for security activities by framing of information security policies, procedures, standards, guidelines and baselines,

Information classification

Security organization and

Security education.

2.1.5 Security Management Responsibilities

Determining objectives, scope and policies,

Evaluate business objectives, security risks, user productivity, and functionality requirements.

Define steps to ensure that all the above are accounted for and properly addressed.

2.1.6 Major challenges of information security system

Database Security: The risk of data security is very high in each educational management information system cell as every individual computer is maintaining its own individual database. Analysis shows that the data is not secure from the virus and can change or alter attack; unauthorized personnel have access to data very easily the data because there is no secure password in 50% of the districts educational management information system Cells computers.

Lack of Information Sharing: Information and data is not completely shared among all the districts. Provincial educational management information system cell distributes annual statistical reports to all districts as a major source of information sharing. Districts do not have direct links with each other for valuable information sharing. If a district wants information about the other district, the request is forwarded to the Provincial educational management information system office where it is either fulfilled or denied if did not found in the central database.

Non-Availability of adequate Information: Annual Statistical Report developed and disseminated to all the districts consists of limited information/data, based on the perceived demands of the users/stakeholders results non availability and inadequacy of data/

information for planning and decision making at all level.

Delay/Slow Data Dissemination Processed:

Data is disseminated to all the districts inform of hard copy Annual Statistical Reports via physical medium, this process takes alot of time in distribution of reports to all the districts. Though report gets also available on the educational management information system intranet but due to unavailability of internet the districts have no access to it.

Delays in Planning and Decision Making at District Level:

At National level, educational management information system is playing significant role in generating targets for policy framework and decisionmaking but at decentralized level educational management information system is not as good as at National level due to lack of capacity constraints and delay in transmission of desired data.

Internet Adoptability and Accessibility:

The use of internet as a method of communication has not been widely adopted in most District educational management information system cells. Majority of the Districts educational management information system cells have internet availability and accessibility.

2.1.7 Condition necessary for standardized security design in Nigerian educational sector

Confidentiality: Confidentiality is a requirement whose purpose is to keep sensitive information from being disclosed to unauthorized recipients. The secrets might be

important for reasons of national security (nuclear weapons data), law enforcement (the identities of undercover drug agents), competitive advantage (manufacturing costs or bidding plans), or personal privacy (credit histories). **Integrity:** Integrity is a requirement meant to ensure that information and programs are changed only in a specified and authorized manner. It may be important to keep data consistent or to allow data to be changed only in an approved manner.

Availability: Availability is a requirement intended to ensure that systems work promptly and service is not denied to authorize users. From an operational standpoint, this requirement refers to adequate response time and/or guaranteed bandwidth. From a security standpoint, it represents the ability to protect against and recover from a damaging event.

2.2 Theoretical framework

Thecla, Chinelo (2020), investigated on management of information security in public universities in Nigeria. They discovered that education information stores immense amount of information which they rely on for effective and hitch free running of their operation.

HuseinAdul-Hamed (2014), examined what matters most for education management system; the study x-rays for policy areas; specifically, enabling environment, system soundness, data quality and utilization of decision making. The study employed situation analysis he found out that management information system is set to use

information generated to improve operational efficiency and educational quality.

Amannah&Ahiakwo(2013) examined Systematic Approach to the Improving Standard of Nigeria Educational System. *The paper examines the root cause of the falling standard of the Nigeria educational system and the rightful solution to these problems. Education is the bedrock of development, but unfortunately, education in Nigeria is bisected with myriads of problems. These include: poor actualise the policies of 14 civilian Presidents and military Heads of States. Many of these policies were laudable. This study also employed situation analysis.*

Al-Awadi and Renaud (2016) opine that information is an asset, and having specific, relevant and correct information can make a massive difference to an organization's efficiency. In view of these reasons, these assets being of utmost importance need to be securely stored and managed. Managing accounts can be laborious, to make this easier, it can be automated. Information security has been established as a core support for mission of organizations and so, would require a comprehensive and integrated approach that will involve both management and staff of organizations.

Due to the fact that there is a great premium attached to the information asset of these organizations, they are vulnerable to the risk of threats from unauthorized persons and entity. Risk in the context of information

security is the outcome the business faces when a threat exploits a vulnerability to successfully attack a target that is being defended

Okpanem (2013) asserts that the only true security system is one that is powered off, cast in a block of concrete and sealed in a lead-lined room with armed guards- and even then there are still doubts. Bearing this in mind therefore, it behooves on the institutions to devise means of managing information security most appropriately. Threats are continually evolving such as spam mails, identity thefts, phishing, data leakage and many more. The primary role of an information security manager is to identify, manage and mitigate security risks on behalf of the organization. In addition to the manager's technical competences, it is also important that the role is carried out within set principles and regulations in order to be able to understand what is, and how it is, allowable by law to carry out this function. Campbell opines that most information security managers in executing their roles, build a process framework known as information security management system (ISMS) that integrates corporate policy with legislation and compliance requirements, linking in external process, procedures and records.

3.1 RESEARCH METHODS

This study made use of an interview survey method in gathering data. The interview method involves questioning and discussing issues with insurance practitioners with respect to standardized security design and information system in Nigeria educational institution. This technique has been seen to be very useful in gathering such data which would likely not be accessible using techniques such as observation or questionnaire [Blaxter, Hughes, Tight, 2006]. The interview is scheduled and structured; and advantageous because of its ability to generally produce fewer incomplete questionnaires, achieve higher completion rates than self-administered questionnaires, and more effective for complicated issues (Babbie, 2005 and Osuala, 2005). The views of respective respondents were coded to improve the completion of the interview scheduled which was drawn using a Likert-type scale measurement of 'Strongly Agree', 'Partially Agree', 'Not Agree'.

The research adopted a survey design and that which was exploratory in nature. The involvement of survey design was because of its ability to predict behaviour and help in gathering the same information about all the cases in a sample [Aldridge, Levine, 2005]. This study employed a judgmental sampling technique because it helped select the unit(s) to be observed on the basis of the researchers' knowledge or judgement of the population, its element and purpose of the study. In a bid to gather relevant information for the study, a

predetermined interview schedule was designed to few selected education institutions in Owerri Imo State, which informed the selection of the surveyed institution. This study thus chooses 3 institution in Imo state; e.g Imo State University, Federal Polytechnic Nekede and AlvanIkoku College of Education the respondents were per institutions.

The questionnaire raised was coded to generate parameters that will fit into multiple regression analysis via ordinary least square method of estimation.

3.2 Model specification

$$Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \beta_3 X_{3i} + \beta_4 X_{4i} + \mu$$

$Y = 1$, if the respondents uses information system in their institution and 0 if otherwise.

X_1 = inter-office

X_2 = firewalls

X_3 = virus protection programmes

X_4 = encryption

μ = Error term.

The main instrument to be used in sourcing the required data is structured questionnaire. The questionnaire is designed and administered to the purposely selected respondents from respondent.

3.3 Decision Rule

At 5% level of significance using t-statistics for the hypotheses tests, the decision to accept or reject the null hypothesis will be based on the following rules:

Accept null hypothesis (H_0) and reject alternative (H_A) if: P-value > 0.05 which would indicate a case no significant effect, impact or relationship. **OR**

Reject null hypothesis (H_0) and accept alternative (H_A) if: P-value < 0.05 which would indicate a case significant effect, impact or relationship.

4.1 Data Analysis and Interpretation

The questionnaire generated were coded to fit in to regression analysis, so as to determine the effect of standardized security design on information system in Nigeria educational institution

Table 4.1 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.867 ^a	.771	.003	.326

R^2 also known as coefficient of determination was obtained as 77.1% which implies that the generated data from field survey strongly determine standardized security design on information system in Nigeria educational institution to the tune of 77.1%

Table 4.2 Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			B	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	.874	.224		3.894	.000	.423	1.325
1 IOC	.115	.006	.259	19.166	.000	.017	.247
VPP	.012	.009	.028	1.333	.845	.106	.130
ENT	.039	.004	.127	-9.750	.000	.127	.049
FW	.058	.007	.128	8.256	.000	.077	.194

H₀: there is no significant relationship between inter-office communication and information system in Nigeria education institution.

Table 4.2 shows that the intercept (β_0) of the models is positive at .874. These indicate that when the independent variables in the model is zero, the dependent variables (Standardize security design) will be positive to the tune of 0.874. The table also reveals that β_1 (the coefficient of inter-office communication) is

positive at .115, these indicate that the first independent variable (inter-office communication) has positive effect on dependent variables (Standardize security design). However, the table also reveals β_2 (the coefficient of the second independent variables) is positive at .058. The implication is the second independent variable (firewalls) also exerts a positive effect on information system in Nigeria education institution.

The coefficient of virus protection and Encryption was obtained as .012 and 0.039

which are positively signed and directly related to information system in Nigeria education institution.

The table also reveals that changes in the independent variables account for about 77.1% changes in information system in Nigeria education institution.

4.2 Test for Significance and Decisions on the Hypotheses of the Study

The t-statistics results from the regression analysis as shown in appendix 2 are summarized in the following table 4.2.

H1: there is no significant relationship between inter-office communication and information system in Nigeria education institution.

The above table 4.2 revealed inter-office communication p-value as 0.000 (i.e. $p < 0.05$); indicating a significant effect exists between the independent variable (inter-office communication) and information system in Nigeria education institution. The study thus holds the null hypothesis to be false and affirm that the inter-office communications significantly affects information system in Nigeria education institution.

H2: there is no significant relationship between firewalls and information system in Nigeria education institution.

Table 4.2 further reveals that the p-value in respect of firewall is .000 ($P > 0.05$) which also shows a significant effect of the dependent variable (information system in Nigeria education institution). The null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative accepted. We thus affirm that firewall has

significant effect on information system in Nigeria education institution.

H3: there is no significant relationship virus protection and information system in Nigeria education institution.

The estimated slope for virus protection revealed p-value of .845 ($P > 0.05$) showing an insignificant relationship with information system in Nigeria education institution. The null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative rejected. We thus affirm that virus protection has significant effect on information system in Nigeria education institution.

H4: there is no significant relationship encryption and information system in Nigeria education institution.

The estimated parameter for encryption revealed p-value of .000 ($P < 0.05$); indicating a significant effect exists between the independent variable (encryption) and information system in Nigeria education institution. The study thus holds the null hypothesis to be false and affirm that the encryption significantly affects information system in Nigeria education institution.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

From the results analysis carried out in this chapter as summarized in tables 4.2; the following findings are made:

The finding from the analysis in relation to the first objective and hypothesis indicated that the inter-office communication shows positive significant effect on information system in Nigeria education institution.

The findings from the analysis in respect of the second objective of this study show that firewalls have a significant effect information system in Nigeria education institution.

The study also revealed that virus protection has an insignificant effect with information system in Nigeria education institution which

led to the rejection of the alternative hypothesis.

The parameter with respect to objective four show that encryption significant affect information system in Nigeria education institution

5.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, information system which is also known as computer-based information system, is important in Nigerian educational systems at all levels because of its transaction process systems, knowledge management systems and information technologies designed to enable individual persons to perform task for which the human brain is not well suited. In addition, the organization of a data system with national coverage is very complex. Studies have shown that there is need for every educational institution in Nigeria to accommodate the use of an information security management system in its operation. The currently existing frameworks for this system have centered much on the use of technology as a means of securing information systems. There is need for information security to become widespread so much so that strategic issues be expunged from the IT domain and aligned with corporate governance approach.

5.2 Recommendation

The following recommendations were proffered as follows;

1. In view of the observed inadequacies in the present policy document there is the need to revise the document. Such revision should be undertaken to involve stakeholders in the area of education so that they can ensure that the policy cover issues related to learning about ICT and learning through ICT.
2. Furthermore, the objectives in sectorial application areas should address education specifically in order

to broaden the market driven objectives. The integration of ICT into every aspect of teaching and learning should also be the key focus.

3. Although the issue of infrastructure is implicit in the present policy it should be reviewed in such a way that access policy is addressed in concrete terms, since this is important in ICT integration.
4. Given the importance of ICT integration in education, the national policy on IT should address the issue of institutions professional development. This should incorporate issues relating to teacher training institutions and ICT, pre-service teacher education, in-service teacher education, and standards for teacher competence and certification in ICT.
5. Also, research, evaluation, and assessment are critical for ICT usage in education. In this context, the national policy should identify a frame of reference in order to gauge success of ICT application in education, such a frame of reference will encourage refinement of school practices relating to ICT integration.

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